

1 **Direct Injection Green Chromatographic Method for Simultaneous Quantification of**
2 **Amoxicillin and Amikacin in Maternity Hospital Wastewater (Sagar, India)**

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4 **Girraj Sharma¹, Priyanka Pahade¹, Abhilasha Durgbanshi², Samuel Carda-Broch³,**
5 **Juan Peris-Vicente⁴, Devasish Bose^{1*}**

6 ¹Department of Criminology and Forensic Science, Doctor Harisingh Gour Vishwavidyalaya
7 (A Central University), Sagar, Madhya Pradesh, 470003, India,

8 ²Department of Chemistry, Doctor Harisingh Gour Vishwavidyalaya (A Central University),
9 Sagar, Madhya Pradesh, 470003, India

10 ³Bioanalytical Chemistry, Department of Physical and Analytical Chemistry, ESTCE,
11 Universitat Jaume I, 12071, Castello, Spain

12 ⁴Department of Analytical Chemistry, Faculty of Chemistry, Universitat de València, 46100,
13 Burjassot-Valencia, Spain,

14
15
16 ***Corresponding author e-mail: devonebose@gmail.com**

17 [0000-0002-8025-6887](tel:0000-0002-8025-6887)

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3
4 **Abstract**

5 Amoxicillin and amikacin are broad-spectrum antibiotics that are most preferably given post-
6 delivery (normal and cesarian) in the maternity hospitals located in the Sagar city (Madhya
7 Pradesh), India. Both the antibiotics make their way through sewage/drainage systems into
8 the environment in the form of metabolized and unmetabolized compounds. Growing concern
9 about the contamination of wastewater by antibiotics required fast, sensitive and eco-friendly
10 techniques. Therefore a simple, rapid and environmental friendly chromatographic method
11 has been developed for simultaneous determination of amoxicillin and amikacin in maternity
12 hospital wastewater samples. A micellar liquid chromatographic (MLC) method was
13 developed with a C₁₈ column (250 mm×4.6 mm), sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS; 0.15 M), 1-
14 butanol (7%) as a modifier, pH 5 and PDA detector at 270 nm and 256 nm for amoxicillin
15 (AMO) and amikacin (AMK) respectively. The method was fast with analysis time below 9
16 min. In the present MLC method, linearities ($r>0.998$), limits of quantification in the range of
17 0.02-0.04 µg/mL, repeatabilities, and intermediate precision below 3.2% were adequate for
18 the quantification of AMO and AMK. The proposed method can be utilized to detect and
19 quantify both the antibiotics in various samples by hospitals, pharmaceutical companies,
20 pollution control board, municipal corporations, etc.

21 **Keywords: Amoxicillin, amikacin, antibiotics, wastewater, maternity hospitals, micellar**
22 **liquid chromatography**

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1 **1. Introduction**

2 Pharmaceutical compounds are complex molecules normally used for various therapeutic
3 purposes according to their properties [1]. Among all pharmaceutical compounds antibiotics
4 are the most important class of drugs used from several decades for human and veterinary
5 treatment of infectious diseases [2-4]. Antibiotics belong to different classes like penicillin,
6 cephalosporin, tetracycline, aminoglycosides macrolides, quinolones etc. Amikacin and
7 amoxicillin are broad-spectrum drugs that belong to aminoglycoside and penicillin class of
8 antibiotics respectively [5,6]. These drugs are marketed in several forms like capsules,
9 tablets, oral or inhale suspensions and intravenous or intramuscular injections [7]. Based on
10 their broad-spectrum applicability both the antibiotics are used individually to treat bacterial
11 infections caused by gram-negative and gram-positive bacteria and in normal or cesarean
12 delivery in maternity hospitals [8].

13 Usually, amikacin is prescribed for the treatment of infection caused by aerobic gram-
14 negative bacillary bacteria [9]. It is specifically used for the treatment of septicemia and
15 infections in skin, bone or tissue, urinary tract, ear, abdominal region etc [10]. It works on
16 bacteria by binding 16 S rRNA ribosomes and starts misreading mRNA which results in the
17 bactericidal effect [11]. Amikacin is also known for causing nephrotoxicity and ototoxicity in
18 the patient after prolong use [12]. Like amikacin, amoxicillin also has wide application for
19 treating bacterial infections such as skin, gastrointestinal, respiratory, tissue, ear, nose, etc
20 [13]. It works by blocking the synthesis of the bacterial cell wall. It also causes bacterial
21 resistance [14]. Bacterial resistance occurs when germs like bacteria and fungi develop the
22 capability to defeat the drugs designed to kill them [15]. These bacteria and fungi may then
23 infect human body and are more challenging to treat when compared to non-resistant bacteria
24 [16].

1 The normal dosage for amoxicillin and amikacin ranges from 20-1500 mg per day.
2 The dose prescribed for adults is 250-1500 mg/day and 15-90 mg/per for pediatric use [9]. It
3 can also be given to the nursing mother. Amoxicillin is metabolized 50% by oxidation and
4 hydroxylation reaction pathway in 6-8 hours and the rest 50% is excreted out in the
5 unmetabolized form [13]. However 94-98% of amikacin is excreted in unmetabolized form
6 within an hour after its administration. So the occurrence of amikacin and amoxicillin in
7 environmental water bodies is posing a great threat to public health due to its increasing
8 consumption [17].

9 Detection of amikacin and amoxicillin antibiotics has been reported by various
10 research groups using different analytical methods such as UV-spectrophotometry [18,19],
11 high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) [20,21] as well as ultra-high-performance
12 liquid chromatography (UPLC) coupled with triple quadrupole mass spectrometry (MS) [22,
13 23]. Both the antibiotics have been analyzed in food [24], pharmaceutical formulations [25,
14 26], biological [27], soil and wastewater [28,29] as well as other samples [29]. Like other
15 methods these methods also have their own limitations as some of the methods are not
16 sensitive and selective in nature, some are highly expensive, time-consuming, per sample
17 analysis cost is too high, and most of them need sample pretreatment before analysis [30].
18 The available HPLC methods for the detection of amikacin in the different matrices need
19 derivatization due to its weak chromophoric properties [31]. However the problem can be
20 overcome using a micellar liquid chromatographic (MLC) method in which the separation is
21 based on the interaction of analyte with the modified stationary phase and pseudo mobile
22 phase. Therefore for the determination of these antibiotics in real samples the developed
23 method should be rapid, simple, sensitive, selective and there should be no need for sample
24 pretreatment. Micellar liquid chromatography is a modified version of reversed-phase liquid
25 chromatography (RP-HPLC) which uses surfactant above the critical micellar concentration

1 as mobile phase. Micellar solutions can solubilize compounds within a wide range of
2 polarities. Therefore, samples with hydrophobic compounds can be directly injected,
3 avoiding column damage and precipitation in the chromatographic system. The technique is
4 able to separate hydrophobic and hydrophilic analyte in isocratic mode simultaneously and
5 the micellar environment also enhances the spectrophotometric activity [32]. Short chain
6 alcohols (1-propanol, 1-butanol, 1-pentanol) are generally added into mobile phase to
7 enhance chromatographic parameters. In addition to solubilization, surfactant monomers
8 form a layer on the outer surface of the stationary phase which modifies its interaction with
9 the analyte. The separation in MLC is generally based on a complex interaction of analyte
10 because the analyte is partitioned between three environments (stationary phase, mobile
11 phase and micelles), thus improving the versatility of MLC.

12 No research work has been carried out for the simultaneous determination of amikacin
13 and amoxicillin in hospital wastewater by using micellar liquid chromatography (MLC) or
14 any other chromatographic methods. Therefore in this research work micellar liquid
15 chromatography was used for the separation and identification of AMO and AMK in
16 maternity hospitals wastewater.

17

18 **2. Materials and methods**

19

20 **2.1. Apparatus and instrumentation**

21 The analytes were weighed using analytical balance from Mettler-Toledo ME204
22 (Pocklington, United Kingdom). The magnetic stirrer and ultrasonic bath (Model USB 6 L)
23 were supplied by PCI Analytics (Mumbai, India). A contech LAB pH meter, Model pH-103
24 (Mumbai, India) with a combined Ag/AgCl/glass electrode was used for pH measurements.

1 The analysis were performed using a liquid chromatographic instrument LC-20AD
2 (Shimadzu, Kyoto, Japan), equipped with an isocratic pump, an autosampler and a photo-
3 diode detector which was connected to a personal computer. The software LC-solution
4 software version 1.22 SP1 was used to control the instrumentation and monitor the signal.
5 The chromatographic separation of AMO at 270 nm and AMK at 256 nm was carried out in
6 isocratic mode. A C₁₈ column, 250×4.6 mm, 5 μm particle size from Shimadzu was
7 equilibrated with the mobile phase for 30 min. at a flow rate of 1.0 mL/min. Each sample was
8 injected using a 20 μL loop injector.

9 10 **2.2. Standards and reagents**

11 The standards of amoxicillin (purity>98.0 %) and amikacin (>98.0 %) were purchased from
12 Sigma Aldrich (Mumbai, India). Sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS, 99% purity), sodium
13 dihydrogen phosphate, and sodium acetate (analytical grade) were purchased from Himedia
14 Laboratories Private Limited (Mumbai, India). HPLC grade 1-propanol, 1-butanol, 1-
15 pentanol were provided by Rankem, RFCL Limited (New Delhi, India). All the solutions
16 were filtered through 0.45 μm nylon membrane filters which were from Micron Separation
17 (Westboro, MA, USA). Type-I Ultrapure water was prepared from Indion LAB Q Ultrapure
18 water generator device.

19 20 **3. Sample collection and preparation**

21 22 **3.1. Sample survey**

23 In India the health system is divided mainly into public and private sectors. Public hospitals
24 normally have all departments under one roof whereas private sector hospitals can have both

1 model i.e. all departments under one roof or dedicated hospitals for a particular field of
2 medicine. One of the best examples of dedicated hospitals are maternity hospitals.

3 Maternity hospitals were selected for this particular study because these hospitals
4 have full occupancy throughout the year and the treatment prescribed by these hospitals is
5 almost similar within the hospital or between different hospitals. The first step in the present
6 study was to locate and identify dedicated maternity hospitals located in Sagar city, Madhya
7 Pradesh, India.

8 Eleven (One public and ten private) dedicated maternity hospitals in Sagar city
9 (**Figure 1**) were figured out. A questionnaire was prepared for the hospitals to survey the
10 trend of antibiotics used post-delivery as well as the number of deliveries (normal and
11 cesarian) carried out each day. It was also enquired whether the hospital was equipped with a
12 wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) and where did the hospital discharge their wastewater.
13 After collecting the desired information a survey was also carried out to trace the outlet and
14 path of the drainage system of the selected hospitals (**Table 1S**).

15

16 **3.2. Sample collection**

17 Wastewater effluent samples from eleven selected hospitals of Sagar city were collected from
18 three points, namely, near, middle and far. The near point was the point at which the hospital
19 wastewater was discharged into the sewage/drainage line. The middle point was somewhat
20 500 meters away from the near point. Whereas the far point was the point where the drain
21 either ends up or mixes with other water bodies. The sample collection strategy included the
22 collection of three samples from each hospital in autumn as well as in spring season. The
23 sample collection was performed during this season as the weather is not too hot
24 (vaporization of water) and not rainy (sample dilution). So the required amount of samples
25 can be obtained in both seasons. Therefore a total of 66 representative samples were collected

1 in 500 mL amber color glass bottle and transported to laboratory in ice box maintaining the
2 temperature at 4°C.

3

4 **3.3. Preparation of the mobile phase, standard and wastewater samples**

5 The micellar mobile phases were prepared by dissolving SDS in ultrapure Type-I water and
6 adjusted to pH 5 using 0.015 M sodium dihydrogen phosphate (NaH_2PO_4) buffer salt. 1-
7 propanol, 1-butanol and 1-pentanol were used in appropriate concentration as organic
8 modifiers. All the mobile phases were filtered through 0.45 μm nylon membrane filters.
9 Individual stock solutions of 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ of amoxicillin and amikacin were prepared by
10 dissolving them in ultrapure water with the help of ultrasonic bath. Wastewater samples
11 stored at 4°C were taken out one hour before analysis (analysed within 24 hours of sample
12 collection). As the samples reached room temperature they were thoroughly shaken and
13 filtered using a 0.45 μm nylon membrane filter for chromatographic analysis.

14

15 **4. Results and discussion**

16

17 **4.1. Sample survey results**

18 In the selected maternity hospitals, the public hospitals were more than 40 bedded and the
19 private hospital had beds in the range of 30-50. As per the data obtained from the medical
20 practitioner, the most preferred antibiotics given post-delivery (normal and cesarian) are
21 amoxicillin and amikacin. The daily consumption of the two antibiotics in public and private
22 maternity hospitals was ranging between 120 to 190 g/day. Regarding wastewater treatment
23 plants (WWTP) both the public and private maternity hospitals had installed WWTP but only
24 three hospitals out of 11 had functional WWTP. Most of the private maternity hospitals

1 discharged their effluents into open drains. These open drains either end up in water bodies or
2 into unused land.

3

4 **4.2. Mobile phase optimization**

5 The first step towards mobile phase optimization begins with selecting the optimum pH. The
6 selection of pH is generally based on the pKa value of the analyte. In this study the pKa value
7 of AMK and AMO were pKa=6.7, pKa=3.2, respectively [33]. These pKa values indicate
8 that both the antibiotics were protonated at pH 3 and 5. At pH 3 AMO was protonated but
9 AMK was somewhat neutral because its pKa value is higher than 3. While moving to pH 5
10 both the analytes have develop a charge on the molecule and get separated within suitable
11 retention time. As the desired results were obtained at pH 5 so it was decided not to study
12 chromatographic effects at pH 7.

13 After selecting the optimum pH the next step in MLC is the selection of surfactant.
14 SDS is the most frequently used surfactant due to its low CMC values, high solubility in
15 water and environmental degradability [34]. Using 0.05 M SDS the retention time (t_R) for
16 AMO was around 6 min whereas that of AMK was 15 min. To reduce the retention time of
17 AMK and to enhance the peak property of both the analytes it was decided to continue further
18 analysis using maximum strength i.e. 0.15 M of SDS with a suitable organic modifier. As the
19 peaks of both the compounds were well resolved it was decided to use 1-butanol to improve
20 the peak parameter. It was 7% 1-butanol which was finally selected and it gave a retention
21 time of 3.0 for AMO and 8.5 for AMK in standard as well as in spike wastewater sample
22 **(Table 1, Figure 2).**

23

24 **4.3. Analytical method validation**

25 ***4.3.1. Calibration and sensitivity***

1 Calibration curves were created using the measured chromatographic area of standard
2 solutions in increasing concentrations up to 10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ in triplicate. To calibrate the
3 developed method fresh standards were analyzed six times over two months. The slope, y-
4 intercept, and the correlation coefficient (r), LODs and LOQs are presented in **Table 2**. The
5 LODs of both the compounds were 0.01 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, while LOQs for AMO and AMK was 0.04
6 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ and 0.02 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ respectively.

7

8 **4.3.2. Trueness and precision**

9 The values of trueness and precision were determined using spiked samples within-
10 laboratory. Maternity hospital wastewater samples collected from different points were
11 spiked at 1, 2.5, and 5 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ using selected antibiotics and analyzed five times by successive
12 injection. The analysis was performed on three different days over a two-month period by
13 preparing fresh samples each time. Recovery was calculated as the proportion between the
14 found concentration of antibiotics and the true value measured by five successive injections.
15 The obtained results in the form of % recovery (trueness) and RSD% (precision) for the intra-
16 and inter-day values have been shown in **Table 3**. For the studied antibiotics the obtained
17 recoveries was in the range of 99.6-103.2% and the relative standard deviation (RSD%) was
18 <3.2%. The results of RSD% were under the value stated by the EPA regulation (15.3%
19 guideline).

20

21 **4.3.3. Robustness**

22 The robustness of the method was examined by replicate injections (n=5) of the standard
23 solution of AMO and AMK at 1 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ level with the slight variations in the concentrations
24 of the main components of the mobile phase (SDS, 0.14–0.16 M; 1-butanol, 6.9–7.1%; and
25 pH 4.9–5.1) [35]. Minor differences in the peak area and low variability in retention time

1 were observed when slight modification in the above-mentioned parameters was applied.
2 However, it does not significantly affect the retention time (<8.5) of antibiotics.

3

4 **4.4. Application of the method**

5 In the nineties of the last century, traces of pharmaceutical compounds present in wastewater
6 were considered as micropollutants but as we stepped into the new millennium, scientists and
7 environmentalists pointed out the potentially harmful effects of pharmaceutical products
8 present in wastewater to flora and fauna. Thirty years later, it is a well-established fact that
9 the minute quantity of these compounds present in the environment can cause hazardous
10 effects to the environment as well as to humans.

11 In order to reduce the discharge of pharmaceutical compounds into wastewater the
12 developed countries treat the wastewater for pharmaceutical compound before being
13 discharged whereas in developing and underdeveloped countries not such treatment
14 procedures are followed for pharmaceutical compounds in wastewater. So these
15 pharmaceutical toxicants are released directly into environmental. It is also important to
16 mention here that many cities in developing and underdeveloped countries do not have a
17 proper sewage treatment plant therefore wastewater is generally discharged in water bodies or
18 unused land near the city or town. Sagar is one of such city where till now no dedicated
19 sewage treatment system is available. The domestic sewage including the hospital waste is
20 dumped into an open drainage system leading to the local water body or barren land near the
21 city. To study the presence of most commonly used antibiotics in maternity hospitals (AMO
22 and AMK) eleven (11) dedicated maternity hospitals in Sagar city were selected. As
23 mentioned in sample collection *section 3.2* a simple survey of the eleven selected maternity
24 hospitals was conducted to know the most commonly prescribed antibiotics post-delivery
25 (normal/ cesarian). It was also surveyed about the wastewater treatment and discharge facility

1 available in each hospital. Irrespective of the fact whether WWTP was available or not
2 wastewater samples were collected from all the selected hospitals. Three collection points
3 were identified and the wastewater was collected. The collected samples were analyzed using
4 the optimized mobile phase.

5 Out of eleven hospitals hospital no. 3 reported maximum concentration of AMO and
6 AMK. The sample which was collected in the spring season (near point) from hospital no. 3
7 gave positive results for AMO and AMK with the concentration of 11.72 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ and 20.38
8 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ respectively. While the concentration of selected antibiotics decreased at middle point
9 (AMO; 6.25 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, AMK 9.31 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) which was further decreased at far point (AMO; 0.20
10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, AMK; 1.18 $\mu\text{g/mL}$). In wastewater sample of hospital no. 5 a moderate concentration
11 5.16 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ and 2.28 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of AMO and 7.95 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, 3.11 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of AMK was found at the
12 near and middle point (**Figure 3**) respectively. In hospital no. 1 only AMO was detected in
13 near and middle point whereas in hospital no. 2 and 7 AMO was detected only at near point
14 and hospital no. 8 showed the presence of AMK at near point. It is pertinent to mention here
15 that hospital no. 4, 6, 9 and 10 did not show the presence of any of the antibiotics either due
16 to the low number of hospitalized patients during the time of sample collection or due to the
17 dilution of wastewater immediately after mixing with the main drainage system. It could also
18 be concluded that when the concentration of the antibiotics was high at the near point it was
19 easy to detect the same at the far point. Whereas the concentration was not very high at the
20 near point it was very difficult to detect them at middle and far points. This could be possibly
21 justified due to its photo degradation or hydrolysis [36].

22 The sample collected in the autumn also gave positive results for AMO and AMK.
23 Both the analytes were detected with a concentration range of 0.15-5.86 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ in the
24 collected sample. In this season, five AMO and three AMK samples were found positive at
25 near points. The maximum concentration 4.20 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of AMO was detected in hospital no. 9

1 while the minimum concentration was (0.15 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) found in the hospital no. 2. In case of
2 AMK, it was detected at very high concentration (5.86 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) in hospital no. 3, while the
3 lowest concentration (0.62 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) was measured in the sample collected from the hospital
4 no. 1. However, both the analytes were not detected at the middle and far points.

5 In all 66 samples (**Table 4**) analyzed in the spring and autumn season thirty-nine
6 samples did not show the presence of selected antibiotics. Based on the data it could be
7 concluded that these conditions arise for cities which either do not have the facility of sewage
8 treatment or could not efficiently treat hospital wastewater separately. Antibiotics like AMO
9 and AMK can easily make their way in un-metabolized form from the hospital to the
10 environment which can pose a real threat to flora and fauna of nearby area.

11 **5. Conclusion**

12 Antibiotics are widely used in human and veterinary treatment and most of them can also be
13 considered as widespread environmental contaminants. The survey results have shown that
14 all the selected maternity hospitals had installed wastewater treatment plants. Still only 33.3%
15 of them were working and most maternity hospitals discharged their wastewater directly into
16 water bodies or unused land without treating them. When micropollutants from these
17 hospitals reached water bodies they cause pathogens resistance and the alteration of microbial
18 diversity. The analytical results also supported the survey as a very high concentration of the
19 unmetabolized form of selected antibiotics was detected in hospital no. 3 (AMO;11.72 $\mu\text{g/mL}$
20 and AMK;20.38 $\mu\text{g/mL}$). In both the antibiotics studied, amoxicillin (sixteen samples
21 positive) is more contaminating the aqueous environment than amikacin (ten samples
22 positive) and posing severe threat to flora and fauna. So there is an urgent need to develop a
23 method that can continuously monitor these micropollutants in water bodies.

1 The developed method was compared with the published result for the determination of
2 AMO and AMK individually using HPLC-UV. AMK was detected in wastewater after
3 sample pretreatment and derivatization and the LODs and LOQs were 2 and 5 times higher
4 than the developed method [37]. Similarly, AMO was also detected in wastewater after
5 sample pretreatment and the LODs was half times higher [38]. Although the LODs of the
6 developed method presented herein is low but the added advantage of the method is that it
7 does not require any sample pretreatment except for filtration, the mobile phase has
8 biodegradable surfactant, making the technique eco-friendly as well as the cost and time of
9 analysis is reduced. The method could easily be used for the detection of these antibiotics in
10 wastewater. Therefore, MLC could be a good choice for this type of analysis. Micellar liquid
11 chromatography was found to be a simple, rapid and sensitive technique for the determination
12 of amoxicillin and amikacin in a wide variety of wastewater samples including maternity
13 hospital wastewater. The developed method allowed the rapid and simultaneous
14 determination of selected antibiotics by direct injection. The total analysis time was within 9
15 min. The method validation was performed according to Environmental Protection Agency
16 (EPA) guidelines with satisfactory results in linearity, trueness, precision and robustness
17 studies. Therefore this method could be routinely used to monitor AMO and AMK in
18 wastewater samples by pharmaceutical companies, pollution control boards, and hospitals.

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1 **Conflicts of Interest**

2 The authors declare that they do not have conflicts of interest.

3 **6. References**

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21 **Figures**

22 Figure 1. Physical map of Sagar city showing the locations of selected maternity hospitals.

23 Accessed on 12 January 2021 from socioeconomic data and application center (sedac).

24 Figure 2. Simultaneous chromatogram was obtained by the analysis of (a) AMO and AMK
25 standard 10 µg/mL (b) AMO and AMK spike in wastewater at 5 µg/mL in the optimized
26 mobile phase.

27 Figure 3. The chromatogram was obtained at middle point hospital no.5 wastewater sample
28 using optimized mobile phase.

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Table 1. Mobile phase study for selected antibiotics along with their separation factors.

Mobile Phase composition	Method development parameters					
	AMO			AMK		
	tr (min.)	N	k'	tr (min.)	N	k'
0.15 M SDS, 1% 1-butanol, pH3	7.8	1656	3.4	6.7	1425	2.8
0.15 M SDS, 1% 1-butanol, pH5	3.4	1254	6.8	7.7	1012	5.9
0.15 M SDS, 7% 1-butanol, pH3	8.2	2264	1.2	8.6	2458	1.5
0.15 M SDS, 7% 1-butanol, pH5	3.0	2564	1.3	8.5	2883	1.5

Table 2. Retention times and calibration data, including calibration range, linear regression, correlation coefficient (r), limits of detection (LODs), and quantification (LOQs) obtained for AMO and AMK using MLC-PDA method.

Analyte	t_R (min.)	Calibration						
		λ max (nm)	Range ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Linear regression	r	LODs ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	LOQs ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	RSD % (n=6)
AMO	3.0	270	0.125-10	$y=13.965+0.632x$	0.999	0.01	0.04	2.03
AMK	8.5	256	0.125-10	$y=3.207+0.366x$	0.998	0.01	0.02	3.64

Table 3. Intra-day (n=5) and inter-day (n=5) trueness and precision for the studied antibiotics

Analytes	Added conc. ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Intra-day			Inter-day		
		Found (Mean \pm SD)	Trueness (%)	Precision RSD (%)	Found (Mean \pm SD)	Trueness (%)	Precision RSD (%)
AMO	1	1.0 \pm 0.09	102	0.9	1.0 \pm 0.07	99.8	2.9
	2.5	2.5 \pm 0.03	99.9	0.8	2.5 \pm 0.03	103.2	1.6
	5	5.1 \pm 0.06	102	1.1	5.0 \pm 0.07	99.9	2.6
AMK	1	1.0 \pm 0.06	98.9	2.3	1.0 \pm 0.07	99.8	3.2
	2.5	2.5 \pm 0.08	108	3.0	2.4 \pm 0.07	101	1.5
	5	5.1 \pm 0.07	102	1.1	5.0 \pm 0.14	99.6	0.9

Table 4. The found concentration of selected analytes ($\mu\text{g/ mL}$) in the maternity wastewater sample

Sampling Site	Location	Spring		Autumn	
		AMO	AMK	AMO	AMK
Hospital 1	Near	1.72	-	-	-
	Middle	1.84	-	-	0.62
	Far	-	-	-	-
Hospital 2	Near	2.22	-	0.15	-
	Middle	-	-	-	-
	Far	-	-	-	-
Hospital 3	Near	11.72	20.38	1.24	5.86
	Middle	6.25	9.31	-	-
	Far	0.20	1.18	1.63	-
Hospital 4	Near	-	-	-	-
	Middle	-	-	-	-
	Far	-	-	-	-
Hospital 5	Near	5.16	7.95	-	4.3
	Middle	2.28	3.11	-	-
	Far	-	-	-	-
Hospital 6	Near	-	-	1.3	-
	Middle	-	-	-	-
	Far	-	-	-	-
Hospital 7	Near	0.25	-	-	-
	Middle	-	-	-	-
	Far	-	-	-	-
Hospital 8	Near	-	1.39	-	-
	Middle	-	-	-	-
	Far	-	-	-	-
Hospital 9	Near	-	-	4.20	3.51
	Middle	-	-	-	-
	Far	-	-	-	-
Hospital 10	Near	-	-	-	-
	Middle	-	-	-	-
	Far	-	-	-	-
Hospital 11 (PuMH)	Near	6.9	1.2	-	-
	Middle	0.1	-	-	-
	Far	-	-	-	-

*blank fields indicate that the analytes are present in lower concentrations than the detection limit or might not be present in the analyzed sample.

Legend

- Maternity Hospital
- Major Roads
- RailwayLine
- Sagar Lake
- City Boundary

Table 1S. A survey related to maternity hospitals, wastewater treatment plants and antibiotic consumption in Sagar city (M.P.) India

S. No.	Hospital	No. of Hospital /beds	WWTP (%)				Per day antibiotic consumption (g/day)	
			Installed (%)	Not installed (%)	Working (%)	Not working (%)	AMK	AMO
1	PuMH	1/30	100	0	0	0	160	120
2	PMH	10/30-50	100	0	33.33	66.66	190	125

*PuMH-Public maternity hospital, PMH-Private maternity hospital